

Supplementary Material

Latent State Modeling of Multichannel Autonomic Signals

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1 Overview

This supplementary document provides extended figures supporting the preregistered H1-H4 analyses reported in the main manuscript. The figures are organized by analytic stage: H1 model search, H2 within-dataset fingerprints, H3 cross-dataset invariance, and H4 cross-dataset generalization.

2 H1 Model Search

Figure S1 shows held-out predictive performance across candidate state solutions for WESAD.

Figure S2 shows held-out predictive performance across candidate state solutions for CASE.

Figure S3 shows held-out predictive performance across candidate state solutions for VitaStress.

3 H2 Within-Dataset Fingerprints

The following figures illustrate representative fingerprint structure from the retained solutions in each dataset.

Figure 1: Figure S1. Held-out predictive log-likelihood across candidate solutions in WESAD. The retained working solution was $K = 6$ under the implemented CASE-standard pipeline.

Figure 2: Figure S2. Held-out predictive log-likelihood across candidate solutions in CASE. The retained working solution was $K = 9$.

Figure 3: Figure S3. Held-out predictive log-likelihood across candidate state solutions in VitaStress. The retained working solution was $K = 7$.

4 H3 Cross-Dataset Invariance

Figures S7-S11 provide additional detail on cross-dataset fingerprint similarity, core correspondences, and dataset-specific tails.

5 H4 Cross-Dataset Generalization

Figures S12-S15 provide supplementary summaries of frozen-definition generalization performance.

Figure 4: Figure S4. Representative WESAD fingerprint figure for the retained $K = 6$ solution. The figure illustrates state differentiation in ECG-based fingerprint structure.

Figure 5: Figure S5. Representative CASE fingerprint figure for the retained $K = 9$ solution. The figure illustrates state differentiation in ECG-based mobilization structure.

Figure 6: Figure S6. Representative VitaStress fingerprint figure for the retained $K = 7$ solution. The figure illustrates state differentiation in PPG-mean-based mobilization structure.

H3 Distance Heatmap: WESAD vs CASE

Figure 7: Figure S7. Fingerprint-distance heatmap for WESAD and CASE states.

H3 Distance Heatmap: CASE vs VITASTRESS

Figure 8: Figure S8. Fingerprint-distance heatmap for CASE and VitaStress states.

Figure 9: Figure S9. Fingerprint-distance heatmap for WESAD and VitaStress states.

Figure 10: Figure S10. Bootstrap stability summary for the strongest three-dataset core triplet correspondences.

Figure 11: Figure S11. Counts of dataset-specific tails identified during invariance analysis.

Figure 12: Figure S12. Primary generalization results summarized as mean predictive log-likelihood under frozen definitions.

Figure 13: Figure S13. Comparison of pairwise triangle tests and leave-one-dataset-out generalization results.

Figure 14: Figure S14. Mean fingerprint distance under cross-dataset generalization tests.

Figure 15: Figure S15. Mean number of common features preserved under frozen-definition generalization tests.